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Demonstrating large Pit Thermal Energy Storages (PTES) and improving their components, processes, and procedures for an accelerated realisation of 100% sustainable DH networks in Europe.

Deliverable 2.1

COMPREHENSIVE APPROACHES FOR PIT THERMAL ENERGY STORAGES SITE SELECTION AND FEASIBILITY ASSESSMENT

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

GA	Grant Agreement
PTES	Pit Thermal Energy Storage
LTES	Large Thermal Energy Storage
IEA-ES	International Energy Agency – Energy Storage
DH	District Heating
GW	Ground Water
DK	Denmark
AT	Austria
DE	Germany
HSE	Health, Safety, and Environment
NIMBY	Not In My Back Yard
TED	Tenders Electronic Daily
IRR	Internal Rate of Return
CHP	Combined Heat & Power

A report compiled based on the contributions from the workshops

This report provides a synthesis of the presentations and discussions that took place during two TREASURE online workshops organized by PlanEnergi, held on May 22, 2024, and June 12, 2024, focusing on "Screening of Location" and "Pre-Feasibility Calculation," respectively. Details of the workshop programs are available in the Appendix (Sections 6.1 and 6.2), and the associated presentations and recordings are included as Annexes to this report.

1. Executive summary

This report offers a thorough evaluation of the methodologies that can be used for Pit Thermal Energy Storage (PTES) site selection, feasibility analysis, and performance assessment, aiming to facilitate well-informed decision-making for future PTES projects.

The initial assessment for a PTES project can be categorized into three main areas: site characteristics (such as space availability, land cost, and proximity to natural areas and DH connection points), local-municipal-governmental regulations, and geotechnical conditions (including the presence of groundwater and groundwater flow, soil properties, terrain topography etc.). Case studies from Denmark, particularly from Hirtshals-Hjørring and Høje Taastrup, provide insights into the challenges and best practices involved in site assessment and geotechnical studies. Additionally, the possibility of constructing a PTES within existing structures, such as landfills or quarries, is investigated. This solution offers benefits like reduced land-use competition, lower costs, and limited environmental impact. However, this approach also presents challenges, including potential site contamination, irregular site shapes, the unavailability of suitable soil for embankments, and inconsistent soil properties or the presence of rock formations. Finally, the report highlights that stakeholder engagement and public perception should be considered at an early stage of the process.

During the opportunity and pre-design phases, it is imperative to conduct comprehensive pre-feasibility calculations that include analyses of energy balance, cost projections, and risk evaluations. Key Performance Indicators play an essential role in evaluating the expected efficiency, and the economic and technical feasibility of a PTES project. A structured approach to data collection is necessary, which can encompass profiles of hourly load, charge and discharge, energy pricing, general cost information, and monitoring data, among others. Various tools, including energyPRO, TRNSYS, and software based on the Modelica language provide strong modeling capabilities to facilitate feasibility studies. energyPRO is noted for its user-friendly interface, making it suitable for high-level energy system analysis and district heating, while Modelica language offers detailed physics-based modelling. TRNSYS is particularly effective for simulation of complicated systems.

Lastly, compliance with European Union directives and tendering processes is essential for obtaining regulatory approvals. The report gives an insight on the EU tender methodology, featuring case studies such as the Fjernvarme Fyn PTES project.

2. Screening of location

Selecting the ideal PTES location involves evaluating key factors such as site characteristics, regulations, and geotechnical conditions. The PTES project in Hjørring-Hirtshals in northern Denmark, serves as a case study of the site selection process. The purpose, methodology, and standards of geotechnical studies are explored, with Høje Taastrup as an example. Additionally, the integration of PTES into existing structures like quarries or landfills is examined. Finally, the stakeholder engagement and public perception are discussed as they are an important part of the process of location screening for PTES project.

2.1 Key considerations for PTES location screening

2.1.1 Summary of the key considerations

Inspired by insights from IEA-ES Task 39 & by Nathan Fournier's presentation, Newheat

The preliminary assessment for a PTES system can be divided into three key categories, summarized in Table 1: site characteristics, regulation compliance, and geotechnical conditions. Each of these factors plays a critical role in determining the feasibility of the project.

TABLE 1: SUMMARY OF THE MAIN CONSIDERATIONS, CHALLENGES AND TOOLS FOR PTES LOCATION SCREENING

Category	Key considerations	Main challenges	Means and tools
Site characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Space availability • Land use and ownership • Cost of land • Proximity to the District Heating (DH) grid • Presence of natural reservoirs areas¹ • Presence of drinking water protection areas • Presence of cultural & historical heritage areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Competing interest for the land, especially in urban areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inputs from local municipality, DH network operator... • Urban planning documents • Open-source tools identifying land availability / ownership
Regulation compliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal framework of the identified locations • Municipal, local, and governmental regulations • Impact of existing and future building developments on project implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of regulation • Site specific regulation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inputs from local regulatory organisms
Geotechnical conditions ²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of Ground Water (GW) & GW flow • Soil properties and quality • Existing buried networks or infrastructures • Terrain topography 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of information regarding soil characteristics & GW condition --> potential need for drilling before securing land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open-source databases³ • Regional geological services • Water authorities • Geotechnical specifications

2.1.1.1 Site characteristics

The first step in the preliminary assessment is identifying suitable sites for PTES implementation. This involves evaluating the available space at each location to ensure that it is sufficient to accommodate the system. A key aspect of this assessment is identifying the ownership of the land, as this will determine the feasibility of securing the site for the project. Land costs are another important consideration, especially in urban areas where space is limited and competition for land is high.

In addition to these practical considerations, the proximity of the site to DH network heat sources and consumers is essential. The efficiency of the PTES system depends on its location relative to these networks, and sites that are too distant may result in increased operational costs and reduced effectiveness. In urban

¹ Natural water-retaining features or ecologically sensitive zones

² This aspect is further discussed in Section 2.2

³ E.g. GEUS, Jupiter, Plandata, and QGIS

areas, competing interests for land, including residential, commercial, and industrial developments, can further complicate the site identification process. This competition can be arbitrated through planning policies that promote net-zero expansion of built environments and prioritization of farmland over other uses.

2.1.1.2 Regulation

Once potential sites have been identified, the next step is assessing regulatory compliance. This includes understanding the legal framework and construction constraints that may affect the development of the PTES system. Urban areas often present additional challenges, such as stricter building codes and land use restrictions, which need to be considered when evaluating each site. A thorough review of site-specific regulations, including zoning laws, environmental impact assessments, and other local rules, is necessary to ensure the project is legally viable.

An important aspect of this process is identifying the permits required for construction and operation. This includes both general permits for building and specific permits related to energy storage systems. The permitting process can vary significantly depending on the location, and it is important to understand what will be required for each site to avoid delays or legal complications. The main authorities to engage with are typically the municipality and the regional government for local regulations, and the state for national-level requirements.

2.1.1.3 Geotechnical conditions

The final component of the preliminary assessment is evaluating the geotechnical conditions of each site. This involves investigating the soil properties, GW levels, and existing underground infrastructures. Understanding the underground conditions is crucial for ensuring the site can support the PTES infrastructure and for identifying any potential challenges, such as poor soil quality or the presence of GW that could complicate construction.

Soil testing and GW analysis are key to identifying any potential showstoppers, such as the need for extensive foundation work or issues related to GW management during both construction and operation. It is recommended to carry out preliminary geotechnical investigation in accordance with the standard specified in Section 2.2.1.4, as shallow initial geotechnical investigations can lead to false conclusions. Additionally, the presence of existing buried networks, such as pipes or cables, must be taken into account to avoid conflicts during construction.

A balance has to be found, in the preliminary phase, between obtaining information on the soil at a given location and the costs associated to these geotechnical investigations. This explains why relying on open-source geological databases and regional geological service websites is often a good first step, with geotechnical investigations likely occurring in a second stage: they are important tools for gathering preliminary information on the site's subsurface conditions (including the presence of bedrock, soil

composition, and soil bearing capacity) and usually freely available. In some projects, involving local utility companies can be beneficial⁴, as they often have the most accurate and up-to-date knowledge of their own piping and cable networks—especially when open-source databases may be incomplete.

2.1.2 Example of the location screening challenges in Hjørring-Hirtshals (DK)

Inspired by Hendrik Wetzel’s presentation, PlanEnergi

To identify a suitable location for the PTES project in Hjørring-Hirtshals, Denmark, several tools were used, including [GEUS](#), [Plandata](#), and [QGIS](#). GEUS, the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland⁵ developed a specialized tool to assess the potential of the upper subsurface for PTES. This tool evaluates key hydrogeological and geotechnical conditions relevant to the project's feasibility.

Three potential areas have been considered as potential sites for the PTES implementation, shown in red in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1: MAP WITH THE 3 IDENTIFIED LOCATIONS FOR THE PTES

⁴ This type of de-risking could also be considered after the initial screening phase.

⁵ An advisory and research institution under the Danish Ministry of Climate, Energy, and Utilities

The main issues summarized in the assessment include:

- **Subsurface and terrain conditions**, involving GW, soil quality, and terrain topography (see Figure 2 to Figure 4 for Area 3⁶)
- **Proximity to the DH grid**
- **Environmental factors**, such as the presence of natural reservoirs and drinking water protection areas (see Figure 5 for Area 3)
- **Planning considerations** include municipal, local, and governmental regulations, as well as the impact of existing and future building developments on project implementation (see Figure 6 for Area 3)

FIGURE 2: DIFFERENT PROPOSED DIMENSIONS AND SHAPES (AREA 3)

FIGURE 3: DEPTH TO GW RESERVOIR (AREA 3)

FIGURE 4: TERRAIN LEVELS (AREA 3)

FIGURE 5: RELATIONSHIP TO PLANNING (AREA 3)

FIGURE 6: RELATIONSHIP TO NATURE (AREA 3)

⁶ Equivalent figures for Area 1 & 2 can be found in Henrik’s presentation during the workshop

Table 2 provides an overview of their characteristics.

TABLE 2: OVERVIEW OF THE 3 IDENTIFIED LOCATIONS AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

Area	Location	Protected Nature	Land Use	Cultural Heritage	Water Interest	Infrastructure	Development Constraints
Area 1 <i>Hirtshals Harbour</i>	Coastal proximity zone near Hirtshals	"Danish Environmental Protection Act §3" protected habitat types, protection under Nature Conservation Act	Recreational area (203-R08), built-up area nearby	WWII cultural heritage in immediate vicinity	No specific drinking water interest	Proximity to built-up area, no major infrastructure constraints	Environmental protection may limit development
Area 2 <i>Snevre to Tornby</i>	Open countryside	"Danish Environmental Protection Act §3" nature conservation areas (mainly grassland)	No current usage plans	None identified	Special drinking water interest (OSD), favorable drinking water area	Transmission line located in immediate vicinity	Limited existing land usage plans, open space available
Area 3 <i>Hjørring East</i>	City proximity zone near Hjørring	No "Danish Environmental Protection Act §3" protected nature areas	Planned traffic facilities, urban development nearby	None identified	Drinking water interest outside OSD (less favorable)	Gas pipeline in area, contaminated soil nearby	Potential contamination and infrastructure conflict

After considering environmental aspects, Area 1 is deemed unsuitable for development due to its protected habitat and other environmental restrictions. When considering proximity to the DH transmission line, Area 2 and Area 3 emerge as the most cost-effective options. Additionally, Area 3 offers the added advantage of being near existing heat production infrastructure, which could potentially increase in- and outlet capacity, reduce operational costs and enhance system efficiency.

To move forward, further investigation should be conducted in collaboration with Hjørring Municipality to explore the feasibility of Area 3. It is crucial to assess whether future local plans align with the existing or planned infrastructure, particularly with respect to the natural gas pipeline in the area. Establishing a PTES facility in this area will require a new planning base, involving the municipal planning authorities, due to the scale of the proposed facility. Further investigations should also focus on GW and soil conditions at the identified location. Considerations regarding heat loss during operation should be addressed as part of the technical planning to optimize efficiency during system operation.

2.1.3 Example of the location screening challenges the demonstration project in Rostock (DE)

Inspired by Uwe Hempfling’s presentation, City of Rostock

Figure 7 illustrates the current DHN in Rostock, featuring a gas-driven CHP (“HKW Marienehe”) and a coal-CHP (“Steinkohle kraftwerk”). These plants supply heat to the DHN when being in operation to produce electricity.

Table 3 provides a summary of the specifications for Rostock’s DHN.

FIGURE 7: MAP OF THE DHN OF ROSTOCK, THE GAS AND COAL CHP PLANTS

TABLE 3: ROSTOCK DHN SPECIFICATIONS

Parameter	Value
DHN length ⁷	Approx. 400 km
Annual heat demand	Approx. 1800 GWh/year (DH + gas)
Power-Plants	75% Gas / 25% Coal
Max Heat Output	Approx. 570 MW
Households DH connection share	Approx. 60 %
DH total supply share	Approx. 45 %

Hamburg Institut helped the city of Rostock to estimate the optimum PTES size of 500'000 m³. Consequently, Rostock aimed to identify at least five primary sites, along with three alternative locations. The City of Rostock and Stadtwerke Rostock also identified additional important parameters for site screening:

- The sites should be distributed on both the east and west sides of the Warnow River.
- Each site should be centrally located and near main pipelines or heat sources.
- There must be sufficient space, with 8 hectares needed for PTES or alternatively
- The availability of the location must be certain or realistically possible.
- The site proportion should be square or rectangular.
- The geology and groundwater situation should be possibly suitable.
- Spatial obstacles due to existing uses and nature protections should be manageable.
- The availability of the location must be certain or realistically possible in a short time.

A total of 32 sites have been identified and evaluated across all involved administrative departments⁸, including Stadtwerke Rostock. Figure 8 is a summary table of the reviews for each site (the lines of the table) made by the administrative departments (with some cells in either green, yellow, or red depending on the level of importance or concern the site represented for the different administrative departments).

Out of these, 5 PTES sites with medium spatial resistance have been selected in accordance with all departments (see Figure 9). The process of clarifying land availability is currently underway. A feasibility study led by the city of Rostock includes soil investigations, preliminary design, and economic calculations.

⁷ Currently in expansion

⁸ Nature protection, urban planning etc.

FIGURE 8: SUMMARY OF THE REVIEWS BY ROSTOCK ADMINISTRATIVE DEPARTMENTS FOR EACH POTENTIAL SITE

FIGURE 9: POSSIBLE PTES SITES⁹

The preferred site is located close to the main transmission pipe and a CHP plant. Further aspects need to be clarified during the project's feasibility assessment.¹⁰

The next steps involve completing the PTES feasibility study. Following this, Stadtwerke Rostock will then proceed with approval and implementation planning. The ultimate goal is to commission the PTES in Rostock between 2028 and 2030.

⁹ Circle with dots means that the feasibility of the site is more uncertain than the circle

2.2 Geotechnical investigation

Inspired by Jan Dannemand Andersen’s presentation, Geo

2.2.1.1 Summary of the key considerations

2.2.1.2 Purpose

The purpose of a geotechnical investigation is to assess the subsurface conditions of a site. This involves a detailed geological survey to determine:

- The types and variations of soil, such as clay, sand, silts or other materials
- GW levels, flow characteristics, and potential variations to understand hydrogeological conditions
- Measurement and estimation of essential geotechnical soil parameters, such as strength, compressibility, and permeability

One key objective is minimizing thermal loss by increasing the height-to-width ratio, though this may be limited by thermal stratification in the water. Additionally, reducing the surface area of the relatively costly lid further supports this optimization. To achieve these goals, excavation should be as deep as practical and economical, while slopes should be as steep as possible within stability limits. However, soil conditions and GW levels are limiting factors.

2.2.1.3 Methodology

Table 4 summarizes the overall methodology for geotechnical investigation studies.

TABLE 4: SUMMARY OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR GEOTECHNICAL INVESTIGATION STUDIES

Type of work	Details
Field work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect soil samples from boreholes (either intact or disturbed). • Conduct in situ tests like Cone Penetration Tests (CPT), Standard Penetration Tests (SPT), and Field Vane Tests (FVT). Other methods may be used based on local practices and the specific soil types • Perform pumping tests from wells (in case of GW lowering)
Laboratory work	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classify geological samples (including geological description, water content, plasticity, and grain size distribution etc.) • Conduct strength tests such as triaxial tests • Perform deformation tests like oedometer tests • Carry out compaction tests (Standard Proctor)
Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare a geotechnical data report • Create a geotechnical interpretation report • Develop a geotechnical design report, including calculations

Site investigations are conducted in multiple stages:

- Desk studies that are based on existing data
- Preliminary investigations for site positioning and preliminary design
- Test drillings and laboratory tests
- Detailed design investigations and optimization studies to refine design parameters
- Continuous monitoring and control during construction and operation

2.2.1.4 Standards

“Eurocode 7 – Geotechnical Design” provides a comprehensive framework for geotechnical engineering. It consists of two main parts:

- Part 1: General Rules – Establishes fundamental principles and guidelines for geotechnical design.
- Part 2: Ground Investigation and Testing – Outlines the procedures for site investigations, laboratory analyses, and field tests to evaluate soil and rock properties.
 - For large-scale structures like PTES, investigation points should be arranged in a grid pattern, with spacing not exceeding 60 meters. Adjustments may be made based on local expertise or intensified in areas with unusual conditions. The grid should also cover surrounding embankments and potentially impacted areas, such as nearby existing structures.
 - The depth of the investigation is also defined by this standard. It varies for the cuttings and embankments and is influenced by the presence of GW (see Figure 39 and Figure 40 in Appendix).
- Additionally, National Annexes allow for adaptations based on local experience and specific safety regulations.

Eurocode 7 is also supported by affiliated standards, including numerous ISO standards that regulate testing methods and technical requirements in geotechnical engineering.

2.2.2 Example of the Høje Taastrup (DK)

Inspired by Per Alex Sørensen’s presentation, PlanEnergi

2.2.2.1 Project characteristics

The 70’000 m³ PTES in Høje Taastrup is operational since 2023. It is connected to the DH network of the Greater Copenhagen.

Figure 11 & Figure 12 depict sketches of the PTES during the pre-design phase.

FIGURE 11: PTES SHAPE

FIGURE 12: OVERALL PTES GEOMETRY

Table 5 summarizes the main PTES characteristics during the preliminary design phase.

TABLE 5: PTES PRE-DESIGN

Attribute	Details
Width x Length	90 m x 200 m
Water depth	16 m
Inner slopes	1:2
Outer slopes	1:1.75
Soil balance	Excavated soil to be used in embankments
Excavation depth	11m
Membrane at the bottom	No insulation
Top of the PTES	Floating insulation lid

2.2.2.2 Geotechnical investigations in Høje Taastrup (DK)

Geotechnical site investigation was conducted by Geo in 2017. 15 boreholes were drilled, including 12 deep ones and 3 shallow ones (see Figure 13).

FIGURE 13: LOCALISATION OF THE BOREHOLES ON THE SELECTED PTES SITE IN HØJE TAASTRUP

The results revealed a surface layer of topsoil (mull), succeeded by a layer of clay till¹⁰/moraine (devoid of any sand layers). Beneath this, a significant deep chalk layer was identified. A principal GW reservoir was located at a depth of 18 meters within the chalk layer, and some local accumulations of GW were found in the sandy till deposits.

Table 6 summarizes the results of the geotechnical studies.

TABLE 6: MAIN GEOTECHNICAL ISSUES TO BE CONSIDERED FOR A PTES FOR HØJE TAASTRUP

Category	Assessment for Høje Taastrup
Excavation feasibility	Possible
Slope stability of excavations ¹¹	Suitable soil --> acceptable slope (1:2)
Re-use of excavated soils in embankments ¹²	Suitable soil --> possible
Slope stability of built-up embankments	OK (1:1.75)
GW handling	No GW lowering & no risk of hydraulic failure ¹³
Risk of permanent GW flow	No significant impact on thermal loss
Risk of thermal dry-out and other effects	Not significant
Possible environmental issues (soil & GW)	Not significant

The geotechnical studies approved the continuation of the project.

¹⁰ Till is a heterogenous mixture of clay, sand, gravel, and boulders varying widely in size and shape

¹¹ Optimizing depth-to-width ratio and lid area

¹² Soil balance

¹³ Heave due to porewater pressure, e.g. if presence of water bearing layers below clay/silt

2.3 Cases of PTES located in existing structures

2.3.1 Key considerations & challenges

Building a PTES in an existing structure such as e.g. a quarry or landfill involves unique considerations beyond those of a conventional excavation-based system (see in Section 2.1.1). One of the key factors is the variability of soil materials surrounding the PTES. In a landfill, the soil composition may be inconsistent, affecting stability and thermal performance, while quarries often feature exposed rock formations with different conductivity properties. Assessing soil parameters such as thermal conductivity, heat retention capacity, and permeability is important.

Another important consideration is location. Quarries are often situated further from urban areas, which can pose challenges in connecting to a DH grid or industrial facilities. This distance may require additional infrastructure investments to transport heat efficiently. Additionally, the potential presence of contaminants, particularly in old landfills, demands careful environmental assessments and mitigation measures to prevent pollution risks. Moreover, unlike purpose-built PTES projects, there may be limited availability of suitable soil for constructing embankments, requiring alternative structural solutions. The irregular shapes of quarries and landfills further complicate the pre-design, making the placement of diffusers and insulation more technically challenging.

On the positive side, using an existing site reduces land-use competition, making PTES integration possibly more cost-effective while also limiting environmental impact compared to excavating a new storage pit.

Table 7 summarizes the main considerations and challenges for PTES located in existing structures.

TABLE 7: SUMMARY OF THE MAIN KEY CONSIDERATIONS & CHALLENGES FOR PTES LOCATED IN EXISTING STRUCTURES

Category	Key considerations	Main challenges
Site characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Space availability • Land ownership • Proximity to the DH grid • Presence of natural reservoirs areas¹⁴ • Presence of drinking water protection areas • Stability of the existing structure (rock integrity in quarries, settlement risks in landfills) • Load-bearing capacity of the site 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of collapse or subsidence (e.g., old landfills, mines) • Ground movement that may affect storage integrity • Proximity to the DH grid (landfills or mines can be far away from dense areas)
Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review the national legislation regarding the repurposing of former industrial sites or infrastructure • Legal framework of the identified locations • Municipal, local, and governmental regulations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Permitting challenges for repurposing a landfill or quarry for thermal storage • Regulations managing potential contaminants
Geotechnical conditions ¹⁵	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential contamination in a landfill (soil testing required) • Soil properties and quality • Presence of GW & GW flow • Existing buried networks or infrastructures • Terrain topography 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of information regarding soil characteristics & GW condition --> potential need for drilling before securing land • Potential difficulties to install the diffuser pipes

Table 8 gives an overview of the advantages and challenges that can be encountered when building a PTES in an existing quarry or landfill.

¹⁴ Natural water-retaining features or ecologically sensitive zones

¹⁵ This aspect is further discussed in Section 2.2

TABLE 8: ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES FOR SPECIFIC EXISTING STRUCTURES

Existing structure	Advantages	Challenges
Quarry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large pre-excavated space • Solid rock may provide thermal buffering and water and diffusion tight surface • Repurposes unused land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential GW intrusion • Structural stability of walls and uneven surface
Landfill	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repurposes unused and potentially contaminated land 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of soil instability and gas buildup • Contaminant leakage risks • Regulatory barriers

2.3.2 Examples

2.3.2.1 Gravel pit in Dronninglund (DK)

Inspired by Per Alex Sørensen’s presentation, PlanEnergi

The 60’000 m³ PTES in Dronninglund (DK) is presently the only PTES project built in an existing structure, a quarry in this case (see from Figure 14 to Figure 16). Some filling material, consisting of bricks, wood, plastic, and other debris from demolished buildings, had to be cleared away, and might have caused some pollution. The soil, primarily composed of sand, was deemed suitable for use in embankments.

FIGURE 14: GRAVEL PIT IN DRONNINGLUND (DK)

FIGURE 15: DIGITAL ELEVATION MODEL WITH CONTOUR SHADING OF THE SITE IN DRONNINGLUND (DK)

FIGURE 16: CONSTRUCTION OF THE PTES IN DRONNINGLUND16 (DK)

2.3.2.2 Basalt quarry near Graz (AT)

Inspired by Maria Moser’s presentation, SOLID

A 1’500’000 m³ PTES is currently being studied for development near Graz, intended to be constructed in a former basalt quarry, as illustrated¹⁷ from Figure 17 to Figure 20), connected to a new solar thermal power plant.

¹⁶ Source: DTU <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0038092X21005120#f0005>

Fortunately, the basalt quarry is located only about 2.3 km from a gas-fired CHP plant, which so far has supplied Graz with heat and is now planned to be decommissioned. Various tests have shown that the surrounding basalt is waterproof, therefore a liner is not required. As a result, excavation and surface sealing costs are eliminated.

The quarry will be filled only up to a water level of 30 meters, below the flowing groundwater table. This minimizes thermal interaction with the groundwater. The basalt also provides additional storage capacity.

One challenge is attaching the lid to the basalt rock and implementing the charge and discharge systems.

FIGURE 17: BASALT QUARRY NEAR GRAZ (AT)

FIGURE 18: COMPUTER GENERATED IMAGE SHOWING THE PTES PROJECT NEAR GRAZ (AT)

¹⁷ Pictures provided by [SOLID](#)

FIGURE 19: TOPOGRAPHY MODEL WITHOUT WATER OF THE GRAVEL PIT NEAR GRAZ (AT)

FIGURE 20: TOPOGRAPHY MODEL WITH WATER OF THE GRAVEL PIT NEAR GRAZ (AT)

2.3.2.3 Landfill site in Hechingen (DE)

Inspired by Inspired by Michael Klöck’s presentation, Solites

In Hechingen, a feasibility study revealed the potential for a 18’000 m³ PTES system, integrated with a new solar thermal plant and the DHN of the new residential area “Killberg IV”. During the landfill’s operational phase, uncontaminated surplus soil from construction sites etc. was delivered and deposited, forming a hill at the outskirts of Hechingen. The feasibility study for the energy supply system for the residential area proved the possibility to use the landfill after closing as location for the PTES and also for a solar thermal plant. After clarification of the related legal aspects, the delivered soil was deposited in the shape of the future PTES, leading to a significant reduction of the PTES costs for earthworks (see from Figure 21 to Figure 24). The delivered soil for the area around the PTES was furthermore checked, pre-selected and compacted in layers during installation to guarantee the static stability.

FIGURE 21: TOPOGRAPHY MODEL OF THE LANDFILL IN HECHINGEN (DE)

FIGURE 22: EARTH LANDFILL BEFORE BEING SHAPED INTO A PTES IN HECHINGEN (02/2023)

FIGURE 23: EARTH LANDFILL BEING SHAPED INTO A PTES IN HECHINGEN (09/2023)

FIGURE 24: PIT ON LANDFILL SITE IN HECHINGEN (10/2023)

2.4 Stakeholder engagement and public perception in an LTES project

Inspired by Michal Klauđa’s presentation, FENIX

Stakeholder engagement is a critical aspect of any large thermal energy project, as public perception and acceptance can significantly influence its success. A key challenge in this process is the “Not In My BackYard” (NIMBY) phenomenon, where people generally support renewable energy but oppose projects when they are directly affected by their impacts. Many citizens acknowledge the importance of climate action but may oppose infrastructure developments due to concerns about visual intrusion, noise, or land use. It is important to involve directly affected stakeholders (landowner(s), neighbours...) early so that they are informed directly and not indirectly through the media. This should however be done with consideration of and in collaboration with the local authorities (typically the municipality) and how they wish to communicate with the local stakeholders.

The [Project Renaissance](#) has examined social acceptance of large-scale energy projects, highlighting key factors in public perception. Economic benefits are a major consideration, but they are not enough on their own; clear communication and well-structured information campaigns are crucial for building trust.

Increasingly, climate change and sustainability concerns influence public opinion, making it essential to highlight the environmental advantages of such projects. The benefits of thermal energy storage and other solutions must be effectively communicated.

Another important finding is the need for greater engagement with younger adults and lower-income groups, who are often underrepresented in energy debates but are key stakeholders in long-term energy transitions. Additionally, there is a growing push to simplify bureaucratic procedures for citizens, making it easier for them to participate in decision-making without undermining the flexibility needed to accommodate diverse energy ecosystems

3. Pre-feasibility calculation

This section explores the key activities, challenges, and tools involved in pre-feasibility calculations for PTES projects. It covers essential technical KPIs and data requirements for performance evaluation during the opportunity & pre-design phase, along with examples of relevant tools, such as energyPRO, TRNSYS, and tools based on Modelica modeling language, such as Dymola or OpenModelica¹⁸.

3.1 Activities, challenges and tools for pre-feasibility calculations

Inspired by insights from IEA-ES Task 39 & by Nathan Fournier's presentation, Newheat

3.1.1 Main activities

The main activities of the Opportunity phase of a PTES project consist of:

- **Identifying the PTES goals**, which may include, for instance, the storage of surplus heat generated from sources such as solar energy, waste heat, or geothermal energy. Additionally, it may involve the storage of heat from a Combined Heat & Power (CHP) plant based on electricity price fluctuations, or peak power shaving, or potentially a combination of these approaches.
- **Gathering PTES boundary conditions**, which requires an evaluation of the energy system heat demand profile on both a daily and seasonal basis. The temperature profile of supply and return lines should be assessed, taking into account seasonal variations. Additionally, space availability should be considered, as it may limit the maximum storage volume.
- **Carrying out a techno-economic assessment** of the PTES project. This begins with initial energetic calculations using early system-pre-design tools. A rough identification of CAPEX, OPEX, and potential subsidies should be performed, along with a preliminary estimate of PTES technical, economic, and environmental impacts.

In the pre-design phase, a more detailed numerical analysis takes place, using advanced tools and models to evaluate performance in different scenarios. The optimization process targets the PTES sizing¹⁹, strategies for charging and discharging, and the overall efficiency of the system. A thorough economic analysis is also necessary, which includes cost estimates, assessments of Internal Rate of return (IRR) and payback periods, as well as finding funding options. The goal is to establish a sustainable economic outlook for PTES solutions.

¹⁸ The software Dymola is typically preferred due to its higher performance, despite requiring a license. However, open-source alternatives like OpenModelica are also available

¹⁹ E.g. the storage capacity in [m³] (which, when combined with delta-T, results in [MWh]), and charging & discharging capacity in [m³/h] (which, when combined with delta-T results, in [MW])

3.1.1 Main challenges

One of the primary challenges encountered is the insufficient availability of comprehensive data regarding heat sources and loads, which encompasses mass flows and temperature fluctuations. Often, the available data is not detailed enough, which requires to make estimations.

Another challenge is the uncertainties related to storage temperatures assessment, which greatly affects the potential use of PTES. Thus, it is crucial to use energy calculations tools early on to model the storage and system behavior dynamically.

There are also significant uncertainties in the early stages of techno-economic calculations, particularly concerning boundary conditions and economic considerations. The simulation results often lack precision, making it difficult to estimate investment costs, operational expenses, and potential returns accurately. This imprecision can stem from the tools or models themselves, or the assumptions made.

3.1.2 Main tools

Numerous tools are available for this phase of the project. A basic tool like Excel or Matlab can serve as an initial approach, although certain factors must be taken into account, such as thermal losses, heat capacity of the PTES and of the inputs/outputs. Dynamic simulation tools such as TRNSYS, energyPRO, Excel/VBA, Matlab, softwares based on Modelica modeling language²⁰, etc. should be used as soon as possible to consider the temperature in the PTES and realistically integrate the PTES into the energy system.

These tools can integrate the primary dimensions of the PTES, provide energy balance calculations on a yearly, monthly, and hourly basis, conduct sensitivity analyses on key parameters, and assist in developing a business plan for the energy system that include the PTES.

3.2 Technical KPIs and data requirements for PTES performance evaluation at the Opportunity phase

Inspired by Carles Ribas Tugores's presentations, AEE INTEC

3.2.1 KPIs for performance evaluation assessment

A list of KPIs has been made for IEA-Task 39, for each project phase (Opportunity, Design, Tender and Implementation & Operation), for different stakeholders (e.g. Policy Makers, Local Residents & General Public, DH Network Operators, Project Owners etc.) and classified by type (Economic, Environmental and Technical). Figure 25 shows the forementioned list at the Opportunity phase. The KPIs list for the other project phases can be found in Appendix (Section 6.4).

²⁰ Such as Dymola or OpenModelica

Actor	Technical indicator	Economic indicator	Environmental indicator
 Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology - Location / land area required - Heat transfer fluid and storage medium - Size of the DHN / heat demand / number of households impacted - Storage lifetime / project start date - Heat source energy fractions with or without LTES & percentage of renewables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Type of impacts to foresee (environment / local residents) - Energy specific CO₂ emissions with or without LTES
 Local residents & General public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology - Location / land area required - LTES volume (compared to concrete values) - Size of the DHN / heat demand / number of households impacted - Storage lifetime / project start date - Heat source energy fractions with or without LTES & percentage of renewables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES 	
 DHN operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology - Location / land area required / distance to integration point - LTES volume - Operation temperature range (Heat transfer fluid AND storage medium) - Heat source energy fractions with or without LTES & percentage of renewables - Identification of post-heating technologies for boosting the discharged temperature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES - Heat generation cost 	
 Project owners / financing stakeholders / developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology - Location / land area required / distance to integration point - LTES volume - Heat source energy fractions with or without LTES & percentage of renewables - Modelled charged and discharged heat - Surplus energy available and targeted heat from the DHN to be addressed - Design storage capacity - Storage lifetime / project start date - Heat source energy fractions with or without LTES & percentage of renewables 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES - Heat generation cost 	

FIGURE 25: RELEVANT KPIS FOR VARIOUS STAKEHOLDERS AT THE OPPORTUNITY PHASE²¹

²¹ Reference: <https://iea-es.org/task-39/deliverables/>

3.2.2 List of needed data at the Opportunity phase

A first overview of data required has been prepared by the consortium and is summarized below.

TABLE 9: LIST OF NEEDED DATA FOR SIMULATIONS

Needed data according to input from the Demonstrators
Load profiles for the heat demand of the DH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Temperatures and thermal power • Hourly data for one year
Charge and discharge profile for the whole year
Heat source(s)
Energy prices
Land available
Specifications of piping network (e.g. DN, flowrates)
Weather data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambient air temperature
General cost data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reference prices of fuels and electricity, CO₂ taxes, CO₂ emission factors of electricity, cost of land, • CAPEX and OPEX of the different heating technologies
Monitoring data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inlet/outlet temperatures • Flow • Temperature measurements in the PTES • Lid heat flux

The TREASURE deliverable titled “Input Data Required and Sources for Simulation Studies on LTES Integration in DH Systems” clearly details the data needed for simulation in the Opportunity phase. It specifies the types of data needed, identifies the stakeholders from whom this data can be acquired, and discusses the relevance of the data in the context of the simulation.

3.3 Examples of tools

3.3.1 energyPRO

Inspired by Niels From’s presentation, PlanEnergi

energyPRO, developed by EMD International A/S, is a leading software for modeling, analyzing, and simulating complex energy projects. It supports cross-sectional optimization including electricity, PtX, hybrid, and thermal energy systems. The software provides detailed technical and financial analyses through a very user-friendly interface, offering clear project overviews and comprehensive reports, including graphical illustrations of the simulations.

Creating an effective model of an energy system that incorporates a combination of storage solutions, solar thermal systems, and/or heat pumps in energyPRO can be challenging. This difficulty arises from the fact that the efficiencies of these components are dependent on their operating temperatures, which are influenced by the interactions among the components. energyPRO can be used to simulate energy systems featuring (seasonal) PTES with some workarounds²², and by accepting some limitations.

Figure 26 illustrates a case study result generated by energyPRO concerning implementation of a PTES into a German DH network linked to a CHP facility utilizing waste incineration.

FIGURE 26: EXAMPLE OF GERMAN CITY WITH WASTE INCINERATION CHP MODELLED ON ENERGYPRO

3.3.2 Software based on Modelica language

Inspired by Carles Ribas Tugores’s presentation, AEE INTEC

The Modelica language is a non-proprietary, object-oriented, declarative, equation-based language designed for acausal modeling of large, complex, multi-domain systems with support for hybrid simulations. It is developed and coordinated by the Modelica Association, a non-profit organization founded in 2000, with members from both academia and industry (e.g., COMSOL, Ansys, BMW, Siemens).

²² E.g. regarding the definition of the storage capacity, the heat losses, the charging & discharging capacity. Niels From’s presentation gives some insights how to handle those workarounds.

Modelica includes both open source and commercial tools and libraries, as summarized in Table 10.

TABLE 10: EXAMPLES OF OPEN SOURCE AND COMMERCIAL TOOLS AND LIBRARIES OF MODELICA

	Examples of tools	Examples of libraries
Open source	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OpenModelica • JModelica 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Libraries for dynamic simulations of thermal and electrical systems at building and district level: e.g. IBPSA, Buildings, ... • Library for “the robust modeling of complex thermofluid architectures” Thermofluid Stream library
Commercial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dymola • SimulationX • Modelon impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air Conditioning Library • FluidDynamics Library

Modelica allows the modeling of energy systems via a graphical interface, see Figure 27. One can make use of available components from commercial and/or open-source libraries²³ or create its own models via the text view, see Figure 28.

FIGURE 27: MODELICA GRAPHICAL MODELLING

```

within Modelica.Fluid.Examples;
model HeatingSystem "Simple model of a heating system"
  extends Modelica.Icons.Example;
  replaceable package Medium =
    Modelica.Media.Water.StandardWater
    constrainedby Modelica.Media.Interfaces.PartialMedium;

  Modelica.Fluid.Vessels.OpenTank tank(
    redeclare package Medium = Medium,
    crossArea=0.01,
    height=2,
    level_start=1,
    nPorts=2,
    massDynamics=Modelica.Fluid.Types.Dynamics.FixedInitial,
    use_HeatTransfer=true,
    portsData=(Modelica.Fluid.Vessels.BaseClasses.VesselPortsData(diameter=
      0.01),Modelica.Fluid.Vessels.BaseClasses.VesselPortsData(diameter=
      0.01));
    redeclare model HeatTransfer =
      Modelica.Fluid.Vessels.BaseClasses.HeatTransfer.IdealHeatTransfer(k=10,
        ports(each p(start=1.le5)),
        T_start=Modelica.SIunits.Conversions.from_degC(20)
          annotation (Placement(transformation(extent={{-90,30},{-60,50}}))););
  Machines.ControlledPump pump(
    redeclare package Medium = Medium,
    N_nominal=1500,
    use_T_start=true,
    T_start=Modelica.SIunits.Conversions.from_degC(40),
    m_flow_start=0.01,
    m_flow_nominal=0.01,
    control_m_flow=false,
    allowFlowReversal=false,
    p_a_start=110000,
    p_b_start=130000,
    p_a_nominal=110000,
    p_b_nominal=130000)
    annotation (Placement(transformation(extent={{-50,10},{-30,30}})));
  Modelica.Fluid.Valves.ValveIncompressible valve(
    redeclare package Medium = Medium,
    CvData=Modelica.Fluid.Types.CvTypes.OpPoint,
    m_flow_nominal=0.01,
    show_T=true,
    allowFlowReversal=false,
    dp_start=10000,
    dp_nominal=10000)
    annotation (Placement(transformation(extent={{60,-80},{40,-60}})));
protected
  Modelica.Blocks.Interfaces.RealOutput m_flow
  
```

FIGURE 28: MODELICA TEXT MODELLING

²³ <https://modelica.org/libraries/>

Figure 29 shows the options provided by the LargeTESModelingToolkit Modelica library²⁴ to model large thermal energy storages (e.g. PTES). The library couples a fluid domain with a ground domain for which different ground layers can be defined.

FIGURE 29: OVERVIEW OF FEATURES OF THE LARGETESMTK²⁴.

3.3.3 TRNSYS

Inspired by Michael Klöck's presentation, Solites

TRNSYS (A TRAnsient System Simulation Programm) is a simulation tool designed for the analysis of complex thermal energy systems, utilizing both algebraic and differential equations. It is a commercial software package²⁵ developed at the Solar Energy Lab (SEL), University of Wisconsin. It features various

²⁴ Reisenbichler-S. Michael, et al. LargeTESModelingToolkit: A Modelica Library for Large-scale Thermal Energy Storage Modeling and Simulation. In proceedings of the 15th International Modelica Conference 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3384/ecp204337>

²⁵ The code is open source, but not free of charge. Some few single types are not open source (e.g. building type 56)

component libraries referred to as "types," which encompasses both standard and non-standard components, including commercial and user-developed models. Within TRNSYS, a number of distinct "types" are available for calculating TTES and PTES with different geometries: cylinders, inverted truncated cones, and inverted truncated pyramids.

The primary benefit of TRNSYS in conducting feasibility studies for DH systems lies in its ability to integrate various components with a high degree of detail for each specific scenario within the overall thermal supply system and comparatively short computing times.

Figure 30 and Figure 31 show examples of possible results provided by simulations using TRNSYS.

FIGURE 30: PTES MODEL IN TRNSYS – VISUALISATION OF WATER AND SOIL TEMPERATURES

FIGURE 31: EXAMPLE FOR INVESTIGATION AND OPTIMISATION - TEMPERATURE DEVELOPMENT IN A PTES

Figure 32 is a screenshot of the TRNSYS Graphical User Interface (GUI), showcasing various "types" that constitute the energy system.

FIGURE 32: EXAMPLE OF TRNSYS INTERFACE FOR A SMALL SYSTEM

3.3.4 Comparison of the different software

Table 11 gives an overview of the pros and cons of the 3 software presented above.

TABLE 11: PROS AND CONS OF THE DIFFERENT SOFTWARE²⁶

Software	Main Pros	Main Cons
energyPRO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User-friendly interface with predefined modules • Good for high-level energy system analysis and DH • Faster to set up a model compared to Modelica and TRNSYS • Easy to learn • Built-in MILP optimizer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited flexibility for detailed PTES modelling • Less accurate for complex thermal storage dynamic: all relevant temperatures must be specified before starting the simulation, and the energy content in thermal storages is based on energy content, not temperatures. • Commercial software with licensing costs
Software based on Modelica language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly flexible, allows detailed physics-based modeling • Open modeling language with some available open source libraries (e.g. Modelica Standard Library) and tools (e.g. OpenModelica)²⁷ • Strong integration with control strategies • Well-suited for transient energy simulations • Modular structure allows customization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Steep learning curve, requires programming²⁸ (Modelica language) • Computationally demanding for complex models • Requires significant expertise to build complex models
TRNSYS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-suited for transient energy simulations • Modular structure allows customization • Open-source (but not free of charge) component models that allow for customization and user-written models • Widely used in renewable energy and thermal storage studies • Fast calculations of integrated energy system, including the storage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be slow when using detailed simulations (3D) of large-scale PTES • Requires knowledge of TRNSYS components • Complex initial model setup, requiring tailored control strategies • Licensing costs of the software and some libraries

²⁶ https://publications.ibpsa.org/conference/paper/?id=simbuild2006_SB06_262_269

²⁷ <https://modelica.org/association/>

²⁸ While working with the graphical interface is possible, it's advantageous to understand the language since model descriptions are typically concise. This knowledge is also helpful for troubleshooting and debugging issues.

4. European tender process for feasibility studies & construction work

Inspired by Søren Brask-Pedersen’s presentation, PlanEnergi

The European tender process for feasibility studies and construction work is discussed, providing insights into the juridical framework, the tender methodology, and taking the PTES project for Fjernvarme Fyn in Denmark as an example.

Figure 33 depicts a summary of the juridical framework and methodology for PTES project tender process. The procedures are fully explained in section 4.2.

FIGURE 33: SUMMARY OF THE JURIDICAL FRAMEWORK AND METHODOLOGY FOR PTES PROJECT TENDER PROCESS

4.1 Juridical framework – EU directives

When the tender is to be made, the relevant European directives must be consulted (see Figure 34). The European Directive on public procurement and the European Directive on procurement in utility sectors— covering entities operating in water, energy, gas, and heat— can be considered. **The European Directive on procurement in utility sectors is the relevant one for the PTES project, as “gas and heat are concerned”.**

<p style="text-align: center;">DIRECTIVE 2014/24/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 26 February 2014 on <u>public procurement</u> and repealing Directive 2004/18/EC</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">DIRECTIVE 2014/25/EU OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 26 February 2014 on procurement by <u>entities operating in the water, energy, transport and postal services sectors</u> and repealing Directive 2004/17/EC</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Article 4</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Contracting entities</p> <p>1. For the purpose of this Directive contracting entities are entities, which:</p> <p>(a) are contracting authorities or public undertakings and which pursue one of the activities referred to in Articles 8 to 14;</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><i>Article 8</i></p> <p style="text-align: center;">Gas and heat</p> <p>1. As far as gas and heat are concerned, this Directive shall apply to the following activities:</p> <p>(a) the provision or operation of fixed networks intended to provide a service to the public in connection with the production, transport or distribution of gas or heat;</p> <p>(b) the supply of gas or heat to such networks.</p>

FIGURE 34: JURIDICAL FRAMEWORK - EU DIRECTIVES

The European Directive on procurement in utility sectors defines 2 threshold values, 443'000 €²⁹ for supply & service contracts (including feasibility study), and 5'538'000 €³⁰ for works contracts, as shown in Figure 35.

- If the estimated tender amount exceeds the threshold, a European tender must be conducted, and the procedure explained in Section 4.2 should be followed.
- If the estimate falls below this threshold, the European directive does not apply, and national rules in the respective country must be followed. Additionally, general European principles apply in cases of cross-border interest. These include transparency, equal treatment, and the obligation to make a public announcement, for instance, on Tenders Electronic Daily (TED).

²⁹ Valid for 2024 and 2025, subject to biennial updates

³⁰ Valid for 2024 and 2025, subject to biennial updates

FIGURE 35: JURIDICAL FRAMEWORK - THRESHOLDS (UTILITY DIRECTIVE)

4.2 Tender methodology – over the threshold amount (EU tender)

If the PTES feasibility study or construction work fall above the thresholds mentioned just above, one of the 6 procedures shown in Figure 36 can be chosen.

- In an open procedure, any interested party is allowed to submit a full tender (see Article 45)
- In a restricted procedure, participation requests may be submitted by anyone, but only pre-selected candidates are permitted to submit tenders (see Article 46)
- In competitive negotiated procedures, participation requests are open to all, but only pre-selected candidates are invited to submit initial tenders and enter negotiations (see Article 47). This procedure may only be used when negotiations are necessary due to the complexity or specificity of the purchase. However, procuring entities in defence, security, water, energy, transport, and postal services sectors may use it as a standard procedure.
- Competitive dialogue is used when a specific need exists, but multiple possible solutions prevent a clear competitive process (see Article 48).
- Innovation partnership applies when no existing market solution is available, and a partnership with a supplier is needed to develop one (see Article 49).
- If competition cannot be established—for instance, if no candidates apply for pre-qualification—direct negotiations with a supplier may be initiated (see Article 50).

<p><i>Article 45</i></p> <p>Open procedure</p> <p>1. In open procedures any interested economic operator may submit a tender in response to a call for competition</p>
<p><i>Article 46</i></p> <p>Restricted procedure</p> <p>1. In restricted procedures, any economic operator may submit a request to participate in response to a call for competition by providing the information for qualitative selection that is requested by the contracting entity.</p>
<p><i>Article 47</i></p> <p>Negotiated procedure with prior call for competition</p> <p>1. In negotiated procedures with prior call for competition, any economic operator may submit a request to participate in response to a call for competition by providing the information for qualitative selection that is requested by the contracting entity.</p>
<p><i>Article 48</i></p> <p>Competitive dialogue</p> <p>1. In competitive dialogues, any economic operator may submit a request to participate in response to a call for competition in accordance with points (b) and (c) of Article 44(4) by providing the information for qualitative selection that is requested by the contracting entity.</p>
<p><i>Article 49</i></p> <p>Innovation partnership</p> <p>1. In innovation partnerships, any economic operator may submit a request to participate in response to a call for competition in accordance with points (b) and (c) of Article 44(4) by providing the information for qualitative selection that is requested by the contracting entity.</p>
<p><i>Article 50</i></p> <p>Use of the negotiated procedure without prior call for competition</p> <p>Contracting entities may use a negotiated procedure without prior call for competition in the following cases:</p> <p>(a) where no tenders or no suitable tenders or no requests to participate or no suitable requests to participate have been submitted in response to a procedure with a prior call for competition, provided that the initial conditions of the contract are not substantially altered;</p>

FIGURE 36: TYPES OF PROCEDURE

Further information about the directives and EU-tender can be found here: www.europa.eu or www.eur-lex.europa.eu.

4.3 Example of a PTES project tender, inspired by Fjernvarme Fyn (DK)

The tender was for the PTES design for Fjernvarme Fyn. Same procedure and evaluation criteria but with less demand of details might also be used for the pre-design and pre-feasibility phase.

4.3.1 General description of the tender

The tender was divided into two parts: the first part covered 700'000 m³, while the second part, for 300'000 m³, was planned for a later stage. The preparation of the tender documents was carried out by the consulting company NIRAS A/S.

For the procurement directive, the directive for entities operating in water and energy sectors was chosen, specifically the "Negotiated procedure with prior qualification competition," which includes a pre-qualification process.

All tender documents are listed in Annex 0.1 (see Table 12). It is essential that they are fully prepared before publication, allowing suppliers to clearly understand the competition.

TABLE 12: LIST OF DOCUMENTS OF THE TENDER MATERIAL FOR FJERNVARME FYN

Annex 0.1
Tender documents
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tender conditions (how to submit the tender, evaluation criteria etc...) • Tender list <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fixed prices for contract services ○ Hourly rates for additional services
Contract documents
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contract (Draft) • Description of services, civil and construction work • Main time schedule • Plan for Health, Safety & Environment (HSE) • ABR18 with precisions and additions (general conditions for consultancy in DK)
Project description documents
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project descriptions, PTES • Project descriptions, civil and construction work
Technical appendix
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description preliminary design (previous reports relevant for the tender) • List of Technical Specifications available • Geotechnical reports incl. appendices

4.3.2 Expected project description in the tender material

The design and feasibility study must include:

- Expense data in the form of volume, utility volume, operating temperatures, flow, etc.
- Design and location of PTES (outline proposal), including access roads
- Choice of materials and insulation
- Inlet and outlet arrangements with pipe dimensions and design, including methods to achieve optimal stratification in the PTES
- The interface with the DH system
- Technical requirements (specific and general)
- Measuring equipment (number, location) and other monitoring
- Handling and disposal of surface water
- Electrical installations
- Handling normal changes in water volume from water expansion
- Security and health in both the execution and later in connection with the operation
- Preparation of construction schedule, including coordination between contractors
- On-site representative during construction phase, e.g. construction-/site manager
- Construction and operation budget

4.3.3 Pre-qualification

Applicants must provide up to five references for similar services completed in the past ten years, specifically related to the design and supervision of membranes and lids for PTES construction. Each reference should include client details, assignment description, consultant services, contract price³¹, and start date³². While the work organization is secondary, the contractor must have started the work within the last ten years. A minimum of two references is required to be considered suitable.

The client plans to prequalify up to three applicants, based on reference evaluations. Selection will prioritize the number, complexity, and size of the references. If more than three suitable applicants exist, the most suitable will be chosen.

4.3.4 Tender evaluation

The contract will be awarded to the tenderer who submits the most economically advantageous tender based on the best price/quality ratio, as assessed on the basis of the sub-criteria detailed in Table 13.

³¹ This will sometimes be difficult to retrieve and is it really necessary as banking statements are usually submitted for larger projects.

³² Period of execution

TABLE 13: TENDER EVALUATION - CRITERIA AND WEIGHT

Sub-criteria	Sub-criteria description	Weighting	Simplified explanation of the grading system
Price	A fixed price is set for the project's described services, while hourly rates apply to estimated extra work. The total price is then evaluated.	20 %	The price is assessed on a scale from 0-10, where a grade of 10 is given to the cheapest price. The other quotation prices are interpolated linearly between the cheapest price and a price that is 30% more expensive.
Organization and staff	The tenderer must outline task organization, specify available employees, and detail key employees' roles and functions in the project.	30 %	The grading system for the qualitative parts also consists of a scale from 0-10 (further described in Table 14 in Appendix)
Process	The tenderer must describe the proposed process for solving the task, including quality assurance, particularly for liner work. Additionally, they must identify expected challenges and risks and propose solutions for managing them.	40 %	
Health, Safety, and Environment (HSE)	The tenderer must describe their approach to HSE in relation to the task, focusing on work environment coordination during the design phase and follow-up during the execution phase.	10 %	

5. Conclusion

Evaluating PTES projects requires a thorough approach that considers technical, economic, and regulatory factors. This report shows that successful PTES implementation relies on careful site selection, thorough feasibility studies, and performance assessments. By understanding land features, environmental limits, and geotechnical conditions, decision-makers can improve site choices and reduce potential issues.

Moreover, the feasibility of PTES is influenced by detailed energy demand analysis, cost-benefit studies, and risk evaluations. Using tools like energyPRO, TRNSYS, and software based on the Modelica language is essential to properly model the PTES and the associated energy system.

Additionally, following European Union rules and tendering procedures is crucial for getting regulatory approvals.

Furthermore, engaging stakeholders and addressing public concerns are important for project acceptance and success. Tackling issues early in the planning phase can help build trust and lead to smoother project implementation.

A project developer looking into the implementation of a PTES should target all above-mentioned points during the early stages of the project, otherwise there is a risk of getting the entire project blocked, or at least a significant delayed, which in turn may increase the costs of the PTES.

6. Appendix

6.1 Programme of Workshop 2.1.A: Screening of location³³

Workshop program 2.1.A: Screening of location	
9:00 - 9:15	•Welcome and presentation of workshop program. <i>Per Alex Sørensen, PlanEnergi</i>
9:15 - 9:45	•Stages in an LTES project and what to be aware of in the opportunity phase. Experiences from IEA ES Task 39. <i>Nathan Fournier, Newheat</i>
9:45 - 10:15	• <u>Case 1</u> : Location screening challenges, based on the examples Hjørring-Hirtshals. <i>Hendrik Wetzel, PlanEnergi</i>
10:15 - 10:30	•Break
10:30 - 11:00	• <u>Case 2</u> : Geological investigations in Høje Taastrup and in which cases is it economical feasible to go below ground water level using cutoff walls, ground water lowering. <i>Jan Dannemand, Geo.</i>
11:00 - 11:45	•Status and problems for the demos, case of Rostock. <i>Uwe Hempfling, city of Rostock</i>
11:45 - 12:30	•Break
12:30 - 12:50	• <u>Reuse of existing structures</u> : Case of Dronninglund. <i>Per Alex Sørensen, PlanEnergi</i>
12:50 - 13:10	• <u>Reuse of existing structure</u> : Case of Hechingen. <i>Michael Klöck, Solites</i>
13:10 - 13:30	• <u>Reuse of existing structures</u> : Case of Graz. <i>Maria Moser, Solid</i>
13:30 - 13:50	•Stakeholder engagement and public perception in an LTES project. And what to be aware of in the opportunity phase. <i>Michal Klauđa, FENIX</i>
13:50 - 14:00	•End of workshop

FIGURE 37: PROGRAMME OF WORKSHOP 2.1.A: SCREENING OF LOCATION

³³ Workshop 2.1.A took place online the 22nd of May 2024

6.2 Programme of Workshop 2.1.B: Pre-feasibility calculation³⁴

Worshop 2.1.B: Pre-feasibility calculation	
9:00 - 9:15	• Welcome and presentation of workshop program. <i>Romain Sucche, PlanEnergi</i>
9:15 - 9:35	• Insights from IEA ES Task 39 on Pre-feasibility calculations. <i>Nathan Fournier, Newheat</i>
9:35 - 9:55	• List of technical KPI's to evaluate the performance. <i>Carles Ribas Tugores, AEE</i>
9:55 - 10:35	• Use of EnergyPRO. <i>Niels From, PlanEnergi</i>
10:35 - 10:50	• Break
10:50 - 11:20	• Examples in Modelica. <i>Carles Ribas Tugores, AEE</i>
11:20 - 11:50	• Examples in TRNSYS. <i>Thomas Schmidt & Michael Klöck, Solites</i>
11:50 - 12:30	• Preliminary experiences and problems met by the demonstrators and solutions how to support the demonstrators. <i>Tbd</i>
12:30 - 13:10	• Lunch break
13:10 - 13:30	• List of needed data for pre-feasibility calculations. <i>Carles Ribas Tugores, AEE</i>
13:30 - 13:50	• How to make an European tender for feasibility studies. <i>Søren Brask-Pedersen, PlanEnergi</i>
13:50 - 14:00	• End of workshop. <i>Romain Sucche, PlanEnergi</i>

FIGURE 38: PROGRAMME OF WORKSHOP 2.1.B: PRE-FEASIBILITY CALCULATION

³⁴ Workshop 2.1.B took place online the 12th of June 2024

6.3 Depths of investigations

FIGURE 39: INVESTIGATION DEPTHS FOR EMBANKMENTS AND CUTTINGS/EXCAVATIONS³⁵

³⁵ Source: Eurocode 7, part 2: Ground investigation and testing

a) Where the piezometric surface and the groundwater tables are below the excavation base, the larger value of the following conditions should be met:

- $z_a \geq 0,4h$
- $z_a \geq (t + 2,0)$ m

where

t is the embedded length of the support; and
 h is the excavation depth.

b) Where the piezometric surface and the groundwater tables are above the excavation base, the larger value of the following conditions should be met:

- $z_a \geq (1,0H + 2,0)$ m
- $z_a \geq (t + 2,0)$ m

where

H is the height of the groundwater level above the excavation base; and
 t is the embedded length of the support.

If no stratum which is slightly permeable to groundwater is encountered down to these depths:

$$z_a \geq t + 5 \text{ m.}$$

Key

1 groundwater

FIGURE 40: INVESTIGATIONS DEPTHS FOR EXCAVATIONS, REGARDING GW³⁶

³⁶ Source: Eurocode 7, part 2: Ground investigation and testing

6.4 Relevant KPIs for various stakeholders for the different project phases

6.4.1 Design Phase

Actor	Technical indicator	Economic indicator	Environmental indicator
 Policy makers		- CAPEX & OPEX	- Hydrogeological effects - Thermal effects and extent of the heating zone - Changes in groundwater chemistry - Changes in microbial population - Reduction in CO ₂ -emissions
 Local residents & General public	- Share of renewables in heat generation portfolio - Share of stored heat in annual heat supply	- Increase/reduction in heat supply tariff	- Hydrogeological effects - Changes in groundwater chemistry - Reduction in CO ₂ -emissions
 DHN operators	- Modelled charged and discharged heat - Number of heat storage cycles per year	- Expected cost of backup heating unit to lift the temperature to the one of DHN	- Hydrogeological effects (i.e. groundwater/ground temperature)
 Project owners / financing stakeholders / developers	- Storage losses - Energy efficiency - Number of heat storage cycles per year - Annual refill volume - Soil characteristics - Slope & depth	- Cost of the energy used to charge the LTES - CAPEX & OPEX	- Hydrogeological effects - Thermal effects and extent of the heating zone - Changes in groundwater chemistry - Changes in microbial population
 General contractors (EPC) & WP contractors	- Design parameters of the corresponding work package LTES components - Performance indicators of the corresponding work package LTES components	- CAPEX & OPEX	
 LTES experts (researchers & engineers)	- All design parameters - Modelled charged and discharged heat - Storage losses - Energy efficiency - Number of heat storage cycles per year	- DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES	

FIGURE 41: RELEVANT KPIs FOR VARIOUS STAKEHOLDERS AT THE DESIGN PHASE³⁷

³⁷ Reference: <https://iea-es.org/task-39/deliverables/>

6.4.2 Tender Phase

Actor	Technical indicator	Economic indicator	Environmental indicator
 Project owners / financing stakeholders / developers	- Key performance indicators of the corresponding work package LTES components	- Updated DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES - CAPEX of the project - OPEX estimations Typically, you can express each Work Package in €/m ³ or €/m ² to easier compare different offers.	Any environmental restriction (and its related KPI) imposed by the administration in the permits obtained needs to be requested
 General contractors (EPC) & WP contractors	- Key performance indicators of the corresponding work package LTES components	- CAPEX of the package	Any environmental restriction (and its related KPI) imposed by the administration in the permits obtained needs to be ensured

FIGURE 42: RELEVANT KPIS FOR VARIOUS STAKEHOLDERS AT THE TENDER PHASE³⁸

³⁸ Reference: <https://iea-es.org/task-39/deliverables/>

6.4.3 Implementation & Operation Phase

Actor	Technical indicator	Economic indicator	Environmental indicator
 Policy makers			- Environmental indicators from the KPI list to control according to regulation
 Local residents & General public		- DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES	- Local area impact during and after implementation (visual, acoustic, traffic disturbance...) - Changes in groundwater chemistry - Ground temperature increase
 DHN operators	- Annual charged and discharge heat - Heat losses - Efficiency - Number of heat storage cycles per year - Auxiliary power consumption	- DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES	- Environmental indicators from the KPI list to control according to regulation
 Project owners / financing stakeholders / developers	- Annual charged and discharge heat - Heat losses - Efficiency - Number of heat storage cycles per year - Auxiliary power consumption - Stratification indicators	- DHN weighted marginal heat price with or without LTES - Evolution of CAPEX & OPEX	- Environmental indicators from the KPI list to control according to regulation - Changes in groundwater chemistry - Ground temperature increase
 General contractors (EPC) & WP contractors	- Performance indicators of the corresponding work package LTES components - Auxiliary power consumption of the corresponding work package LTES components	- Evolution of CAPEX & OPEX	
 LTES experts (researchers & engineers)	- Measurements from the various sensors of the project - Stratification indicators - Efficiency		- Environmental indicators from the KPI list to control according to regulation - Changes in groundwater chemistry - Changes in microbial population

FIGURE 43: RELEVANT KPIS FOR VARIOUS STAKEHOLDERS AT THE IMPLEMENTATION & OPERATION PHASE³⁹

³⁹ Reference: <https://iea-es.org/task-39/deliverables/>

6.5 Tender evaluation – example of the PTES project for Fjernvarme Fyn

TABLE 14: TENDER EVALUATION - CRITERIA FOR QUALITATIVE PARTS

Grade	Description
10	Awarded for the outstanding tender that best meets the sub-criterion with no or few insignificant exceptions
9	Awarded for tenders with an exceptionally good fulfilment of the sub-criterion
8	Awarded for tenders with very good fulfilment of the sub-criterion
7	Awarded for tenders with good fulfilment of the sub-criterion
6	Awarded for tenders with less than good fulfilment of the sub-criterion
5	Awarded for tenders with a moderately satisfactory fulfilment of the sub-criterion
4	Awarded for tenders with slightly below average satisfactory fulfilment of the sub-criterion
3	Awarded for tenders with less satisfactory fulfilment of the sub-criterion
2	Awarded for tenders with poor fulfilment of the sub-criterion
1	Awarded for tenders with very poor fulfilment of the sub-criterion
0	Awarded for a tender that meets the overall evaluation criteria, despite the absence of supporting information demonstrating compliance with the individual sub-criteria

